

Observations of Pigmy Owl (*Glaucidium passerinum*) and Three-toed Woodpecker (*Picoides tridactylus*) in Mt. Durmitor, Montenegro

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Abstract: Localities of Pigmy Owls (*Glaucidium passerinum*) and Three-toed Woodpeckers (*Picoides tridactylus*) have been recorded in October 2014 in the old-growth coniferous forests of Mt. Durmitor, Montenegro. Both species are very rare glacial relicts found in few occasions in that country.

Key words: Pigmy Owl, Three-toed Woodpecker, Montenegro, Durmitor

Pigmy Owl (*Glaucidium passerinum*) and Three-toed Woodpecker (*Picoides tridactylus*) are rare and endangered species in the Balkan peninsula, having highly fragmented distribution and considered as glacial relicts (SIMEONOV et al., 1990; NANKINOV et al., 1997). Their distribution and numbers are actively studied during the last 20 years in Bulgaria and Serbia (SHURULINKOV et al., 2003, SHURULINKOV et al., 2012, SPIRIDONOV et al., 2008 RAJKOVIC et al., 2013) but are not well known in the Western Balkans, especially in Montenegro, Albania, Macedonia and Kosovo.

During a two day field expedition in the forest zone of Mt. Durmitor, Montenegro (1. to 2. 10.2014) we conducted daytime transects using sound imitations of the voice of Pigmy Owl and Three-toed Woodpecker. Imitation was played at points situated at every 500 metres. On 1.10.2014 we passed the route from Ivan Dol through Zmijno Lake, Surdup and up to Crepulj poljana (about 5 km).

Pigmy Owl was found at two localities and Three-toed Woodpecker also at two localities, all of them on 1.10.2014. First record of a Pigmy Owl was made in a 100-150 years old spruce (*Picea abies*) forest with some firs (*Abies alba*) at Zmijno Lake, 1520 m.asl., at 12:00 hrs. The bird was a male which was heard to perform its mating song. After that it was attracted by our playback and was observed at a dis-

tance of 10 m and photographed (Fig.1). The second Pigmy Owl was also attracted and observed in 100-years old spruce forest with beech (*Fagus sp.*) and fir at 1600 m asl., at 650 m from the first locality of the same species (13:30 hrs). That bird performed only alarm call.

Three-toed Woodpecker was found also at two places, at a distance of 780 m between them. First locality was at "Surdup" area where one female was observed and photographed (Fig.2). The forest was 100-years old spruce forest with presence of beech and fir, on a very steep slope, at 1590 m asl. The bird was feeding on a dry tree. It was first heard knocking on the bark of the tree and then seen by us without acoustic provocation. The second Three-toed Woodpecker was male and was observed again without sound provocation in a 120-years old spruce-fir forest, at 1568 m asl. At this locality some cut trees were present which was probably made for sanitary cutting. The percent of the dry standing trees in both localities of Three-toed Woodpecker was in frames of 3-5%.

Pigmy Owl was reported as a possible breeding species in Montenegro for the area of Kolašin where one individual was observed from 5 m in Austrian Pine (*Pinus nigra*) forest on 2.05.1978 (RAŠAJSKI & GAVRILOV, 1983). The total population of the Pigmy Owl in Montenegro was estimated at 3-5 breeding

Fig. 1. Pigmy Owl (*Glaucidium passerinum*), Mt. Durmitor, 1.10.2014, photo: Peter Shurulinkov

Fig. 2. Three-toed Woodpecker (*Picoides tridactylus*), Mt. Durmitor, 1.10.2014, photo: Peter Shurulinkov

pairs and in Serbia at 5-10 pairs (PUZOVIC et al., 2003). In neighbouring Bosnia and Herzegovina the species is reported to be a regular breeding species with preliminary numbers estimated at 50-100 pairs (KOSTROŠAN & HATIBOVIC, 2012).

Three-toed Woodpecker has been observed at Mt. Durmitor in 1890 (REISER & FUHRER, 1896) and recently between Zabljak and Crno Lake on 28.07.2004 (STEINER, 2004). The species was mapped as a breeding bird in two 50X50 UTM squares of

Montenegro (HAGEMEIJER & BLAIR, 1997) The total population of Three-toed Woodpecker in Montenegro was estimated at 40-80 breeding pairs (PUZOVIC et al., 2003).

In Serbia the Three-toed Woodpecker is a very rare species and nests mostly in mountain massifs situated in the southwestern parts of the country – at Prokletije, Kamena gora, Zlatar, Kopaonik and Tara and the numbers were estimated at minimum 5 pairs (VASIC et al., 2009).

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Наблюдения върху малката кукумявка (*Glaucidium passerinum*) и трипръстия кълвач (*Picoides tridactylus*) в планината Дурмитор, Черна Гора

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(Резюме)

През октомври 2014 г бяха установени находища на врабчова кукумявка (*Glaucidium passerinum*) и трипръст кълвач (*Picoides tridactylus*) в стари иглолистни гори в планината Дурмитор, Черна гора. И двата вида са много редки глациални реликти регистрирани в единични случаи в тази държава.